

Event metadata

Event title	Our journey incorporating AI into our cancer computational research
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	11/06/2024
Time of event	12pm AEST
Topic description	<p>This event is part of the Webinar series: “AI in the life sciences: Exploring possibilities, inspiring change”.</p> <p>Join us for a series of webinars where we explore how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is shaping the future of life sciences!</p> <p>This series provides an accessible introduction to AI while giving direct access to experts and practical insights into real-world applications. Designed to inspire and help you recognise potential applications of AI in the life sciences, these webinars will spark new ways of thinking so that you can start applying AI in your work.</p> <p>The webinars include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A foundational session covering AI basics, its evolution, and why it matters for life sciences. Watch the recording here! - Guest speaker sessions where leading experts from academia and industry share how AI is being applied in different domains - Live Q&A to engage with speakers, ask questions, and participate in discussions <p>Dr. Anna Trigos session focuses on exploring the real-world challenges that many researchers face before any models are built or predictions made. Expect practical reflections, and inspiration for those at the beginning of their own AI journeys.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and

	answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/ai-series-2025
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	<p>Is this series for me?</p> <p>Are you:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Curious about AI but unsure how it applies to your work? - Working in life sciences and want to understand how AI is shaping the field? - Interested in learning from experts on domain specific AI applications? - Keen to explore ethical challenges in AI-driven research? - Looking for trusted resources to continue your AI learning journey? <p>If you answered yes to any of these questions, then this series is for you!</p>
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	
Speakers	Dr Anna Trigos, Group Leader, Peter MacCallum Cancer Center
Training materials	<p>Materials shared in this Zenodo record:</p> <p>Event metadata (PDF): Information about the event including, description, event URL, learning objectives, prerequisites, technical requirements etc.</p>

	<p>AI_presentation_Trigos (PDF): A PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar.</p> <p>Materials shared elsewhere: A recording of this webinar is available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube Channel: https://youtu.be/vCkGbWuyLaQ</p>
Related material	None